

ROLE OF MICROBIOME IN PATHOGENESIS OF BRONCHIAL ASTHMA, ALLERGIC RHINITIS

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Abstract. *The article presents modern data on the role and influence of the state of the microbiome of various mucous membranes and skin in the process of formation and course of bronchial asthma, allergic rhinitis. New therapeutic approaches to the correction of microbiotic disorders for the prevention and treatment of allergic pathology (bronchial asthma, allergic rhinitis) in adults and children are clearly demonstrated.*

Key words: *microbiome, bronchial asthma, allergic rhinitis*

Аннотация. *В статье представлены современные данные о роли и влиянии состояния микробиома различных слизистых оболочек и кожи в процессе формирования и течения бронхиальной астмы, аллергического ринита. Наглядно продемонстрированы новые терапевтические подходы к коррекции микробиотических нарушений для профилактики и лечения аллергической патологии (бронхиальной астмы, аллергического ринита) у взрослых и детей.*

Ключевые слова: *микробиом, бронхиальная астма, аллергический ринит.*

Annotatsiya. *Maqolada bronxial astma va allergik rinitning shakllanishi va kechishida turli shilliq pardalar va terining mikrobioma holatining roli va ta'siri haqida zamonaviy ma'lumotlar keltirilgan. Kattalar va bolalarda allergik patologiyaning (bronxial astma, allergik rinit) oldini olish va davolash uchun mikrobiotik buzilishlarni tuzatishning yangi terapevtik yondashuvlari aniq ko'rsatilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *mikrobioma, bronxial astma, allergik rinit.*

In recent years, the potential role of the human microbiome in modulating immunological tolerance and the pathogenesis of allergic diseases has been actively studied. By definition, the microbiome is a collection of microorganisms (MO) (bacteria, fungi, archaea, and protozoa) and viruses that colonize a given environment and physiologically and sometimes pathologically coexist in a symbiotic relationship with the human body [1]. The microbial world constantly interacts with the human body. We are in daily contact with an infinite number and countless varieties of microbes in the environment. Some bacteria can pass through the body without causing any harm, while others can cause undesirable health consequences [2].

An increase in various allergic pathologies is noted annually. Many authors note that such a rapid change in the prevalence of allergic diseases among children could not be caused by global evolutionary processes and genetic predisposition, so the emphasis on cause-and-effect relationships has shifted towards changes in the environment, as well as in lifestyle. More and more people prefer to live in large cities, the lifestyle of which implies certain features of nutrition and hygiene. The total number of children in families has also decreased, which reduces microbial diversity due to more serious attention to hygiene issues.

It has been proven that lifestyle changes, the transition from a diet with a predominantly high fiber content to a diet high in fats and proteins, as well as the choice in favor of cesarean section and bottle feeding affect the composition of the microbiome [3]. Due to the development of medicine, vaccination, and health literacy of the population, the number of infectious diseases

has significantly decreased, which undoubtedly affected the overall picture of morbidity of the population [4].

In 1989, a concept known as the hygiene hypothesis of the increase in the prevalence of allergic diseases was presented. Researchers have suggested that improved methods of sanitizing food and housing, the development of medicine, the use of antibacterial drugs and various antiseptics have led to a decrease in the incidence of infectious and parasitic diseases. This, in turn, led to a change in the nosological landscape and led to an increase in allergic pathology with a parallel decrease in the proportion of infectious diseases. Quite a large number of works have been published proving that the interaction of microbes with the host organism results in stimulation of regulatory immune mechanisms. The interaction of microbes with the host organism, both from the outside and with the human microbiome itself, stimulates immune regulation with a predominance of the Th1 vector of immune reactions [5]. Conversely, the depletion of the microbiome, in particular the intestinal microbiome, together with a decrease in the proportion of parasitic and bacterial infections due to improved hygienic conditions, inevitably leads to an increase in Th2-mediated immune reactions. Thus, to date, it has been proven that a decrease in the proportion of parasitic and microbial infections was expressed in a decrease in ROR γ ⁺Treg-regulatory B cells producing interleukin 10. This in turn led to a shift in the vector of immune reactions towards Th2 reactions with the development of hypersensitivity to previously harmless antigens, such as pollen or food [6,7].

In support of the positive influence of the microbial and parasitic world on the development and course of allergic diseases, recent studies have shown that immunoglobulins G (IgG) induced by the flatworm schistosome exhibit blocking properties with respect to IgE Ara h1, Bet v1, Phl p1, Phl p 5b. The reactivity of IgG-schistosome was mainly due to similar glycans present on helminths and plants, which is manifested by blocking activity with respect to allergic reactions to pollen and peanuts [8, 9]. Another mechanism of blocking the effect of allergic reactivity was demonstrated using the molecule of transforming growth factor β - a protein with a cytokine-like function produced by many parasites, which is able to use the endogenous pathway of immunoregulation in the host organism. This molecule can induce Foxp3⁺Treg cells. Together, they can potentially bind to IgE and block Fc ϵ RI on mast cells [10].

It is obvious that the microbiome as a whole, as well as the microbiota of the skin and gastrointestinal tract, can synergistically and independently influence the development and course of allergic diseases. At the same time, a significant number of factors can influence the formation of the microbiome. And currently, the starting point for the formation of the microbiome is no longer the path of childbirth, but the landscape of the mother's microbiome during pregnancy and even conception [11].

Innovations in the molecular field, in particular the amplification and sequencing of the gene encoding 16S ribosomal RNA, have made it possible to obtain a large amount of data on the different types of bacteria present in the body. The data obtained made it possible to create so-called biogeographic maps of the MOs living in areas of the body such as the skin, intestine, oral mucosa or vagina [12].

The first studies aimed to find links between the onset of allergic diseases and environmental factors using epidemiological data and developing the so-called hygiene hypothesis: it was found that respiratory allergies or atopic dermatitis are more common in children from small families than in children from large families. Further studies showed that children who spent the first years of their lives in rural areas, in close contact with animals and consumed unpasteurized milk had a lower incidence of allergies [13].

These studies have suggested a role for the microbiome in these diseases, identifying some neonatal and maternal factors that may influence the development of the immune system in the first months of life and thus determine a key role in the potential for the development of allergic diseases [14].

During pregnancy, the fetus experiences intrauterine contact with maternal microbes [15]. The placenta has been shown to not only function as a source of nutrient exchange but also to have a rich metabolic microbiome. In utero microbial exposure is associated with altered fetal innate immune gene (TLR) expression profiles in the gut. Notably, recent studies have shown that innate immune features can be modulated by dietary interventions in the mother's diet using specific probiotics and by changing the place of residence during pregnancy [11,16]. Studies have shown that women who were pregnant in an agricultural environment had increased numbers and efficiency of Treg lymphocytes, which was accompanied by altered cytokine profiles in the cord blood of newborns with a predominance of the anti-inflammatory vector.

The microbial population in the amniotic fluid, despite its low abundance, richness and diversity, can also influence the formation of the fetal microbiome [17], which is confirmed by the presence of a microbial landscape in the meconium of the newborn that is almost identical to that in the amniotic fluid. The most common in the amniotic fluid are various proteobacteria with a high abundance of species belonging to the Enterobacteriaceae family, such as *Enterobacter* and *Escherichia/Shigella*, some types of *Lactobacillus*, *Staphylococcus* and *Streptococcus* [17]. As for bifidobacteria, by the time of birth of the child, this type of monophyletic (identical to the maternal) microorganisms is detected in the meconium of the child, which indicates intranatal translocation of these bacterial strains. It is noteworthy that among children born by cesarean section, monophyletic bifidobacteria are practically not observed [18]. In support of the positive influence of the microbial environment on the formation of the child's microbiome, the results of studies conducted on newborns born vaginally or by caesarean section have been published, showing that the colonization of various areas (skin, mouth, intestines) consists of species such as *Sneathia* and *Lactobacillus* spp. (bacteria present in the birth canal of mothers in labor), while in children born by caesarean section, there is a predominance of *Staphylococcus* and *Streptococcus* spp. These results confirm previous epidemiological studies that have shown a reduced risk of developing allergic diseases in children born vaginally [19].

The concept of a single inflammation of the upper and lower respiratory tract, based on the phenomenon of solidarity of the mucous membranes, has been described in detail in a number of studies and underlies the formation of an inflammatory cascade, clinically determining the phenotypes of the disease [20,21]. Studies of the potential relationship between the microbiome and bronchial asthma (BA) and allergic rhinitis (AR) were prompted by the discovery of the lung microbiome through DNA amplification using 16S RNA, which subsequently led to a revision of the theory of sterility of the lower respiratory tract [19]. However, earlier, back in 2010, M. Hilty et al. conducted a cultural study of bronchial lavages of 20 children, 17 of whom suffered from BA, and seven constituted the control group. As a result, it was demonstrated that in patients with BA, the bronchial tree microbiome is represented mainly by bacteria of the genus Proteobacteria, including the genera *Haemophilus*, *Moraxella* and *Neisseria*. In the control group of healthy children, the microbiome was represented predominantly by MG of the Bacteroidetes genus *Prevotella*, which constitutes the normal flora of the oral cavity [22]. Subsequently, a study by R.P. Dickson et al. showed that MG of the Firmicutes type are also widespread in healthy people, although they usually colonize the upper respiratory tract [23,29].

In 2007, a prospective study included 411 newborns born to mothers with asthma. An analysis of the microbiota collected from hypopharyngeal aspirates at the age of one month was conducted. These children were then monitored until the age of five years. Throughout the observation period, episodes of laryngotracheitis and obstructive bronchitis were recorded. As a result of observation, it was found that children colonized in the hypopharynx area with such microorganisms as *S. pneumoniae*, *H. influenzae* and *M. catarrhalis*, or a combination of these microorganisms, were at higher risk of recurrent episodes of obstructive bronchitis and bronchitis at an early age [24,28].

A number of studies indicate a lower incidence of bronchial asthma in children living in rural areas compared to those living in large cities. It is assumed that contact with wildlife, the prevalence of unprocessed food in the diet (pasteurization and other industrial processing of food products) help reduce the risk of developing bronchial asthma [25,26].

This article presents current data on the role and influence of the state of the microbiome of various mucous membranes and skin in the process of formation and course of allergic diseases. New therapeutic approaches to the correction of microbiotic disorders for the purpose of prevention and treatment of allergic pathology in adults and children are clearly demonstrated.

The relationship between the intestinal landscape and diseases of the bronchopulmonary system was demonstrated relatively recently. During the experiment, two groups of mice were isolated, one of which was fed dust from houses where dogs lived. As a result, it was found that mice fed with house dust, when stimulated with various allergens, as well as respiratory syncytial virus, showed a significantly less pronounced inflammatory reaction from the bronchial tree compared to the control group. The mice of the experimental group also showed a high concentration of *Lactobacillus johnsonii*, which indirectly indicated the protective effect of the intestinal microbiome on allergic reactions of the lungs [26,30].

Further evidence has been provided by recent studies in mice showing that a diet rich in fermented foods containing Firmicutes and Bacteroidetes MOs increases short-chain fatty acids that inhibit dendritic cells mediating the Th2 response, thereby providing protection against allergic lung inflammation [27].

Thus, such a diverse microbial environment during pregnancy and birth influences the expression of innate immune genes in the infant, allowing the neonate to be more tolerant of the microbial environment outside the womb after birth [20].

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